

PARTICLE SIZE AND FREE IRON OXIDES DISTRIBUTION ALONG TWO TOPOSEQUENCES IN SOUTH WESTERN NIGERIA

Enya, O.O, Omueti, J.A.I and Akinbola, G. E.
Agronomy Department, University of Ibadan, Ibadan. Nigeria.

ABSTRACT

Particle size and free iron oxides content distribution along Sedimentary and Basement complex toposequences in South Western Nigeria was investigated. Representative soil samples totaling nine mini-pits (45 cm x 45 cm x 70 cm) were taken based on topographic position. Conventional methods were used in the determination of pH, particle size distribution while the free iron oxides were determined using Dithionite-Citrate-Bicarbonate (DCB) and Acid Ammonium Oxalate methods. Results indicated that, soil texture was loamy sand surface horizon and increasing proportion of clay with depth, except the valley bottom profile in the basement complex toposequence which was clayey on the surface horizon, decreasing with depth. Silt content showed that those of basement complex have an average of 105.4 g/kg while those of sedimentary formation were 32 g/kg. pH values of the soils ranged 4.9 to 6.0 indicating strongly acid to medium acid. Dithionite extractable Fe oxide was 51.5 g/kg and 16.8 g/kg at Basement Complex toposequence and Sedimentary toposequence respectively. Oxalate extractable Fe were low (9.1 g/kg) at Basement Complex toposequence and (6.0 g/kg) at the Sedimentary toposequence. Basement Complex toposequence have low Fe-ratio and could be highly weathered as compared to the Sedimentary formation. This may be due to the coarse nature of the Sedimentary formation. There is high negative significant correlation between $Fe_d/clay$ and clay content in Sedimentary formation ($r=-0.913$; $p<0.01$) and high positive significant correlation when $Fe_d/clay$ was correlated with silt ($r=0.887$; $p<0.01$) in Basement Complex toposequence, indicating co-migration of Fe and clay and Fe and silt respectively.

KEYWORDS: particle size, free iron oxides, sedimentary and basement complex toposequences, dithionite extractable, oxalate extractable.

INTRODUCTION

The majority of the total irons found in soils exist as oxides. These oxides are found as iron concretions as well as coatings on the soil minerals or bind the different soil particles (Olsen, 1948) Particle size and free iron oxides distribution has been extensively studied at both small and large scales (Juo *et al.*, 1973; Udo, 1980; Ogunsola and Omueti, 1990; Mosugu *et al.*, 1999; Agbenin, 2003; Igwe, 2005; Obi and Akinbola, 2009) . This work is to further contribute to the existing works that has been done on the sedimentary and basement complex toposequences in South Western Nigeria compared with other regions.

Forms of free iron oxides are important parameters for the proper understanding of the soil. Their amount and distribution in the soils are known to influence some soil properties such as anions adsorption, surface charges, specific surface area, swelling and aggregate formation, nutrient transformation and pollutants retention in soils (Deshpande *et al.*, 1968; Greenland *et al.*, 1968). The various forms of free iron oxides have been extracted by different extractants (Mehra and Jackson, 1960; Mckeague and Day, 1966; Holmgren *et al.*, 1967; Blumme and Schwertman, 1969; Blakemore *et al.*, 1987; Walker, 1983). Dithionite extractable Fe and Al have been widely considered to give a reasonable estimate of the total pedogenic free iron oxides in soils.

The pattern of distribution of free iron oxides is closely related to that of clay where clay content is more than 40% in the B horizon and closely related to silt for soils less than 40% clay (Juo *et al.*, 1973; Udo, 1980; Ogunsola and Omueti, 1990; Mosugu *et al.*, 1999; Ibia, 2001). Relative contribution of oxalate extractable to total iron oxides (DCB extracts) is low (0.01 -0.36%) in soils overlying limestone areas in Southern Nigeria suggesting that Fe oxides were essentially crystalline (Ogunsola and Omueti, 1990). Also, the dithionite iron extractable (Fe_d) content increases with increase of depth and the constant clay/dithionite Fe-ratio indicates the co-migration of clay and Fe oxides from the A horizon into the B horizon (Juo *et al.*, 1973; Ogunsola and

Omueti, 1990; Agbenin, 2003). The crystalline form of free iron oxides had been found to dominate in the basement complex soils of South Western Nigeria (Ogunkunle and Onasanya, 1992; Obi and Akinbola, 2009). Topography is one of the five main factors of soil formation that influence the way soils develop. According to (Moormann, 1981; Okusami *et al.*, 1985), strong associations exist between topography and soils. In the basement complex regions, topography is closely related to the underlying parent rock (Smyth and Montgomery, 1962; Ogunkunle, 1990; Ogunkunle and Onasanya, 1991; Ogunkunle, 1993)

A good knowledge of particle sizes and Fe oxides distribution along sedimentary and basement complex toposequences is necessary for easy management of the soil as well as enhancement in agricultural production. Texture of the soil plays an important role in soil structural development resulting to nutrient availability in the soil due aggregate formation. For instance, clay content may indicate the ability of the soil to supply or retain applied plant nutrient while sand and silt determined the degree of soil weathering and the relation between soils and their parent materials. Phosphate management problems in weathered tropical soils are mostly associated with the abundance of free Fe and Al oxides (Agbenin, 2003). Also, percentage of free iron oxides have long been used as means of differentiating Soil type, Soil horizon and in the determination of soil age or degree of soil development (Mckeague and Day, 1966; Bascomb, 1968; Blume and Schwertmann, 1969). The present study was aimed at knowing how particle size and free iron oxides are distributed along sedimentary and basement complex toposequence in South Western Nigeria. This can be achieved through the following objectives, by determining;

1. The particle size and free iron oxides in the soils profiles along each of the toposequences.
2. The factors responsible for the variation observed in the two toposequences

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The site: The toposequences are located at Ajibode (one of the major geological formations in the University of Ibadan) and at Ilishan-Remo (Ogun State). Ajibode toposequence lies between E003⁰53' and N07⁰27' while Ilishan-Remo toposequence lies between E003⁰41' and N06⁰53'. The slope gradient ranged from 0-9⁰ at the crest/upper slope to 0-8⁰ at the lower slope and is gently rolling to rolling with occasionally rock outcrops at the basement complex toposequence. The mean annual rainfall is about 1500mm, with the rainy season occurring between April and November. The mean monthly temperature ranges between 24⁰ and 28⁰C. The original rainforest has given way to derived savanna because of intensive farming activities. Ilishan-Remo Site is currently used for cassava cultivation and some palm trees while part of the land is under fallow. Ajibode Site was under fallow at the time of sampling with evidence of arable (maize, cassava, and pineapple) farming in the previous years.

Field Work and Analysis

Representative soil profiles were selected based on topographic position and mini-pits (45 cm x 45 cm x 70 cm) were sunk. The profiles were described using FAO/UNESCO (2006) guide lines. Soil samples were collected for laboratory analysis into well-labeled sampling bags using a spade, starting from the last horizon upwards in order to avoid contamination from the horizons. Soil samples were air-dried, crushed gently with pestle and mortar, sieved using 2 mm sieve to remove materials greater than 2 mm. Particle size distribution was determined by the hydrometer method (Bouyoucous, 1951). The procedure involves taking a 50 g air dried soil samples which passed through a 2 mm sieve. The 50 g soil samples were poured in dispersion cup and 10 ml of 5 % Calgon solution was added. The Calgon act as a dispersing agent. 100 ml of water was added to the suspension and the dispersion cup containing the suspension was mixed using mechanical shocker for 5 minutes. The suspension was then transferred to a glass cylinder with all soil particle rinsed into the cylinder with water. The volume of the cylinder was made up to 1000 ml mark, stopped and then thoroughly mixed. Hydrometer was inserted gently into the suspension in the cylinder and the first hydrometer reading was taken at 40 second and corresponding temperature reading. The suspension was allowed to stand for two hours and second hydrometer reading was taken with corresponding temperature reading using thermometer.

The hydrometer reading at 40 seconds gives the weight of the silt plus and clay fractions in the suspension while the second hydrometer reading (At two hour) gives the clay fraction in the suspension. The hydrometer was calibrated at 20⁰C so that any temperature above or below this requires a temperature correction factor. The correction factor is $\pm 0.3 \times t^{\circ}\text{C}$ (where t = temperature in degree Celsius) the textural class of the soil was determined using FAO, 2007 guidelines.

Soil pH was determined using pH meter with glass electrode in 1:2 (soil: water) and (soil: 1NKCl) ratio.

Dithionite citrate bicarbonate extractable Fe was determined using the combination of Mehra and Jackson (1960) and Holmgren (1967) procedures: Extraction solution was prepared by dissolving 425 g of Na citrate in 2.1 litres of distilled water and 41.7 g of Na dithionite and makes up to 2.5 litres of distilled water. 1 g of fine earth (pass through 0.5 mm Sieve) was weighed into 120 ml plastic bottles + 2 blanks. 60 ml of citrate/dithionite reagent was added to the sample bottle + 2 blanks and was shake for 16 hours 35 ml of the suspension was transferred into centrifuge tube and 3-4 drops of superfloc solution was added mix and centrifuge for 10 minutes at 2,500 rpm. The clear supernatant was then carefully decanted into a 100 ml volumetric flask and the solution was read using AAS at x 5 and x 50 dilution.

Acid ammonium oxalate extractable Fe was determined using Mckeague and Day (1966) and Blakemore *et al.*, (1987) procedures. The extraction solution was prepared by dissolving 40.5 g NH₄ Oxalate and 27 g of oxalic acid in 2.25 litres of distilled water and makes up to 2.5 litres at pH 3. 1 g of air dried soil sample (passed through 0.5 mm Sieve) was weighted into a 100 m shaking plastic bottle plus 2 blanks and a reference sample. 50 ml acid oxalate reagent were added and closed and was shaken in the dark for 4 hours 35 ml of the solution was transferred to a 50 ml centrifuge tube. 3-4 drops of superfloc solution was added, swirl well and centrifuge x 5 and x 20 dilutions was prepared using 2.38 g KCl and 25 ml Conc. HCl to 1 litre distilled water for x 5 dilution while 2.01 g KCl, 210 ml acid ammonium oxalate solution and 21 ml Conc. HCL to 1 litre of distilled water. The Fe was measured by AAS at 248.3 nm using an air/acetylene flame.

Statistical Analysis

The data were analyzed statistically using SPSS (originally, Statistical Package for the Social Sciences)

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Morphological Properties

Table 1 shows the morphological characteristics of the sedimentary toposequence. The topographic position includes crest, upper slope, middle slope and valley bottom. The soils are well drained, dark brown (7.5YR 3/2) surface horizons to reddish (10R 4/6 and 10R 4/8) sub soils with angular to medium – sub angular blocky peds. The consistence (moist) ranged from friable to very firm down the profiles. The soils are overlying sandstone parent materials with no observable inclusions. Moss (1957) reported that these soils are of Alagba series. Table 2 shows the morphological characteristics of the basement complex toposequence. The topographic position includes crest, upper slope, middle slope, lower slope and valley bottom. The drainage pattern ranged from well drained to poorly drain along the toposequence. This may be due to gently rolling to rolling with occasionally rock outcrops nature of the toposequence. The soils have dark brown (7.5YR 3/2) surface horizons to yellowish red (5YR 5/8 and 5YR 4/6) sub soils with angular to medium – sub angular blocky peds. Consistence (moist) ranged from friable to very firm along the toposequence. Fe and Mn concretions within 100cm depth tending to formation of plinthite were present. Clay and re-oxyhydroxides elluviation – illuviation under oxidizing conditions has been reported by Payton (1993a, pp. 703-723) and Esu, (2005, pp. 41) as processes resulting in the formation of plinthite. Smyth and Montgomery (1962) reported that these soils are of Iwo associations derived from banded gneisses and are very extensive in basement complex of south western Nigeria.

Particle Size Distribution

Data for particle size are presented in Table 3. Location A profiles are generally sandy clay loam while location B profiles varies from sandy loam (crest), sandy clay loam (upper and middle slope) to sandy loam (lower slope and valley bottom). A close look at their clay contents showed that proportion of clay increased with depth, except the lower slope and valley bottom profiles. This may be due to alluvial accumulation of soils or yearly deposition of fresh materials down the slope. This agreed with Ogunsola and Omuetti (1990, PP. 111) in soils overlying limestone areas in Southern Nigeria. Ogunkunle (1993, pp.339) reported that, the difference in the clay contents between the upper and lower slope positions in basement complex soils of South western Nigeria is a common feature reflecting the effect of soil transportation and deposition. Silt content showed that those of location B have mean silt content of 105.4 g/kg while those of location A have mean 32.0 g/kg. This difference in silt content may be a reflection of the content in their respective parent materials.

Chemical properties:

The PH values of the soils ranged from 4.9 to 6.0 indicating strong acid to medium acid (Table 4). This is a reflection of leaching characteristic of high rainfall areas. The dithionite extractable Fe have mean values of 16.8 g/kg and 51.5 g/kg while oxalate extractable Fe mean values was 9.1 g/kg and 6.0 g/kg at sedimentary and basement complex toposequences respectively. It is generally considered that dithionite extractable Fe will

extract iron from both crystalline and amorphous source while oxalate extractable Fe is essentially amorphous in nature (McKeague and Day, 1966; Blume and Schwertmann, 1969).

There is no obvious regular pattern in the distribution of the free Fe in the profiles. Generally, it could not be established that all the B-horizons have higher Fe_d or Fe_o . This may be due to the fact that iron movement is partially independent of clay movement. Similar observation was reported by Ogunsola (1986, pp.96) in soils overlying limestone areas in Nigeria. The means of the Fe-ratio was low and were less than unity (0.56 and 0.30) at the sedimentary and basement complex toposequences respectively (Table 3), indicating that basement complex toposequence could be highly weathered as compared to the sedimentary formation. This may be due to the coarse nature of the sedimentary toposequence. However, mineralogical properties were not determined. There is high negative significant correlation between Fe_d /clay and clay content in toposequence A ($r=-0.913$; $p<0.01$) while toposequence B was significant when Fe_d /clay was correlated with silt ($r=0.887$; $p<0.01$), indicating co-migration of clay and silt with depth respectively.

The co-migration of iron oxides for other Nigerian soils has been reported by various workers (Ashaye, 1968 Juo *et al.*, 1973; Udo, 1980; Ogunsola, 1986; Ogunsola And Omueti, 1990).

CONCLUSION

Particle size and free iron oxide distribution along sedimentary and Basement Complex toposequences in South Western Nigeria is complex. The more undulating Basement Complex toposequence exhibits more variation than the Sedimentary toposequence. The study has provided relevant information which, if used, will enhance the proper management towards higher agricultural productivity.

REFERENCES

- Agbenin J. O. (2003). Extractable iron and aluminum effects on phosphate sorption in savanna alfisol. *Soil Science Society of America Journal* 67: 589-593.
- Ashaye, Y. I. (1968). Sequioxide status and particle size distribution in twelve Nigerian soils derived from sandstone. *African Soils Journal* 14: 83-96.
- Bascom, C. L. (1968). Distribution of pyrophosphate-extractable iron and organic carbon in soils of various groups. *Journal of Soil Science* 19: 251-268.
- Blume, H. P. and Schwertmann, U. (1969). Genetic evaluation of profile distribution of aluminum, iron, and manganese oxides. *Proceeding of the 33th Soil Science Society of America*. 438-444
- Bouyoucouc, C. J. (1951). Hydrometer method improved for making particle size analysis. *Agronomy Journal* 43: 434-438.
- Esu, I. E. (2005). Characterization, classification and management problems of the major soil orders in Nigeria. 26th Inaugural Lecture of the University of Calabar 10-16, 41-42.
- FAO/UNESCO. (2006). Guideline for soil profile description: World Soil Resources Report. Rome.
- Holmgren, G.G.S. (1967). A rapid citrate-dithionite extractable iron procedure. 24th *proceeding of the Soil Science Society of America*. 420-421.
- Juo, A. S. R., Moormann, F. R. and Maduakor, H. O. (1973). Forms and pedogenetic distribution of extractable iron and aluminum in selected soils of Nigeria. *Geoderma* 11: 167-179.
- McKeague, J. A. and Day, J. H. (1966). Dithionite and Oxalate extractable of iron and aluminum as aids in differentiating various classes of soils. *Canadian Journal of Soil Science* 46: 13-22.
- Mehra, O. P. and Jackson, M. L. (1960). Iron oxide removal from soils and clays by a Dithionite-Citrate System Buffered with Sodium Bicarbonate. *Clays and Minerals*. 5: 317-327.
- Moss, R. P. (1957). Soil survey report on classification of the soils found over Sedimentary Rocks in Western Nigeria. 67: 1-11.

Obi, J. C., Akinbola, G.E. and Anozie, H. I. (2009). Distribution of Dithionite and Oxalate- extractable iron oxides of a Catena in the Basement Complex soils of South Western Nigeria. *Nigerian Journal of Soil Science* 19(1): 100-109.

Ogunkunle, A.O. (1990). Topographic location, soil characteristics and soil classification in three biogeological location in Mid-Western Nigeria. *Malaysian Journal of Tropical Geography* 19: 22-32.

Ogunkunle, A. O. and Onasanya, O. S. (1993). Soil Landscape relationship in a forest zone in South Western Nigeria. *Samaru Journal of Agricultural Research* 9: 19-33.

Ogunkunle, A. O. (1993). Variation of some soil properties along two toposequences on Quartzite Schist and Banded Gneiss in South Western Nigeria. *An International Journal of Physical, Social, and Economic Geography and Application in Environmental Planning and Ecology* 30.4: 397-402.

Ogunsola, O. A. (1986). Characterisation of soils overlying limestone areas in Nigeria. Ph.D. Thesis. Depart. Of Agronomy, University of Ibadan 96.

Ogunsola, O. A. and Omueti, J. A. I. (1990). The physical, chemical and mineralogical characteristics of soils overlying limestone areas in Southern Nigeria. *Nigeria Journal of Science* 24: 110-118.

Payton, R. W. (1993). Fragipan formation in argillic brown earths (Fragiudalfs) of the Milfield plain, North East England II. Post Devensian developmental processes and the origin of fragipan consistence. *Journal of Soil Science* 44: 703-723.

Smyth, A. J. and Montgomery, R. F. (1962). Soils and land use in Central Western Nigeria. *The Government Press, Ibadan-Nigeria*.

Udo, E. J. (1980). Profile distribution of iron sesquioxides content in selected Nigerian soils. *Journal of Agricultural Science Cambridge* 95: 191-198.

Walker, A. L. (1983). The effects of magnetite on Oxalate-and Dithionite- extractable iron. *Soil Science Society of America Journal* 47: 1022-1026.

Table 1: Soil Morphological Characteristics of Ileshan-Remo Profiles

Depth (cm)	Horizon	Colour (moist)	Structure	Consistence	Boundary	Inclusion	Roots
Crest							
0-20	A	7.5YR 3/2	m-sbk	Fr	CS	-	C
20-70	Bt ₁	10R 4/8	f-sbk	Fm	CS	-	Fw
70-100	Bt ₁	2.5YR 3/6	f-abk	Vfm	CS	-	vf, fw
100 – 120	Bt ₂	2.5YR 4/8	f-abk	Vfm	CS	-	vf, fw
Upper slope							
0-21	A	7.5YR 5/8	m-sbk	fr.	Sc	-	C
21-39	Bt ₁	2.5YR3/6	m-sbk	fr.	CS	-	Fw
39-67	BC ₁	2.5YR 4/6	f-abk	fm,sl.st	CS	-	Fw
67-100	BC ₂	2.5YR 3/6	f-abk	vfm, sf	CS	-	Fw
100-130	BC ₃	10R 4/8	f-abk	vfm, vsf	CS	-	-
Middle slope							
0-32	A	5YR 3/3	m-cr	fr, sl, st	Cw	-	m-fw
32-53	Bt ₁	2.5YR ¾	m-sbk	fr. sl.st	CI	-	C
53-70	Bt ₂	10R ¾	m-sbk	fm, st	CI	-	f, fw
53-70	Bt ₂	10R ¾	m-sbk	fm, st	CI	-	-
70-100	Bt ₂	10R4/8	m-sbk	fm, st	CI	-	-
100-120	Bt ₂	10R4/8	m-sbk	vfm, vst	CI	-	-
Valley Bottom							
0-28	A	7.5YR 3/2	f-cr	fr.	CS	-	vf, mg
28-70	Bt ₁	10R3/6	m-sbk	fm, st	CS	-	vf, fw
70-100	Bt ₂	10R 4/8	m.abk	vfm, sl.st	CS	-	vf, w
100-120	Bt ₂	10R4/8	m-abk	vfm, sl.st	CS	-	-

m – sbk = medium sub-angular blocky, fr= friable, CS – clear smooth, C = common
 f-sbk = fine sub-angular blocky, fm = firm; fw = few, v = very
 abk = angular blocky, Cr = crumbs, sl= slightly, st= sticky
 Cw= Clear wavy CI = Clear irregular, Ma = Many.

Table 2: Soil Morphological Characteristics of Ajibola Pedons

Depth (cm)	Horizon	Colour (moist)	Structure	Consistence	Boundary	Inclusion	Roots
Crest							
0-18	A	7.5YR 5/3	m-sbk	Fr	CS	-	fw, m
18-38	Bt ₁	5YR 4/4	m-sbk	Fr	CS	-	fw, f
38-70	Bt ₂	5YR 4/6	m-sbk	Fr	CS	Stone mottles	Fw
70-100	BC	5YR5/8	m-sbk	Fr	-	Fe/Mn	Fw
Upper slope							
0-15	A	7.5YR 3/3	m-sbk	Fr	CS	-	Fw
15-25	Bt ₁	5YR 4/6	m-sbk	Fr	CS	-	C
25-54	Bt ₂	5YR 4/6	m-sbk	Fr	CS	Fw mottles	-
54-100	BC	5YR 5/8	m.sbk	Fr	CS	Fe, cutans	-
Middle slope							
0-25	A	7.5YR 3/3	m-sbk	Fr	CS	-	Fw
25-33	Bt ₁	5YR 5/8	m-sbk	Fr	CS	-	Fw
33- 70	Bt ₂	5YR 4/6	m-sbk	Fr	CS	Fe/Mn, cutans mottles	-
70-85	BC	5YR 5/8	m-sbk	Fr	CS	M mottles	-
Lower slope							
0-18	A	7.5YR 3/4	Abk	Fm	CS	-	fw, f
18-33	Bt ₁	7.5YR 6/8	Abk	Fm	CS	-	fw, m
33-70	Bt ₂	5YR 5/8	Abk	Fm	CS	-	fw, f
70-100	Bt ₂	5YR 4/6	Abk	Fm	CS	Fe/Mn	fw, f
Valley Bottom							
0-10	A ₁	10YR 4/4	Abk	fm, vst, v hand	CS	-	fw, f
10-30	A ₂	5YR 3/2	Abk	fm,vst	CS	-	fw, m
30-70	Bt ₁	5YR 5/8	Abk	fm,vst	CS	-	-

m = medium sbk = sub-angular blocky, fr= friable, CS – clear smooth, fw = Few, C = common, f = fine, v= Very, fm = Firms, st= sticky

Table 3 Physical Properties of Two Toposequences within South Western Nigeria

Location	Topographic Position	Sand	Silt	Clay	Texture
		g/kg			
A	Crest	662	29	309	SCL
	Upper slope	664	14	322	SCL
	Middle slope	636	46	318	SCL
	Valley bottom	670	39	291	SCL
	μ	658	32	310	
	SD \pm	15.05	13.88	13.78	
	CV%	2.29	43.38	4.45	
B	Crest	752	74	174	SL
	Upper slope	677	94	229	SCL
	Middle slope	613	99	288	SCL
	Lower slope	711	99	190	SL
	Valley bottom	599	161	240	SL
	μ	670.4	105.4	224.2	
	SD \pm	64.7	32.75	44.81	
	CV%	9.65	31.07	19.99	

SCL= Sandy Clay Loam, SL= Sandy Loam

A= Sedimentary Toposequence

B= Basement Complex Toposequence

μ = mean

SD \pm = standard deviation

Cv%= coefficient of variation

Table 4 Chemical Properties of Two toposequences within South Western Nigeria

Location	Topographic	PH	PH	Fed	Feo	Fed-Feo	Feo/Fed
	Position	H2O	KCl	g/kg			
A	Crest	5.1	4.3	17.5	8	10	0.46
	Upper slope	5.2	4.5	20.3	8.9	11.4	0.44
	Middle slope	5.2	4.4	16.8	10.4	6.4	0.62
	Valley bottom	5.9	5.3	12.6	9.1	3.5	0.72
	μ	5.4	4.6	16.8	9.1	7.8	0.56
	SD \pm	0.37	0.46	3.18	0.99	3.57	0.13
	CV%	6.85	1	18.92	10.88	45.77	23.21
	Crest	5.6	4.7	20.4	6	14.4	0.29
	Upper slope	5.4	4.4	13.4	4.4	9	0.33
	Middle slope	5.2	4.4	13.8	4.8	9	0.35
B	Lower slope	5.6	4.7	11.9	4.5	7.4	0.38
	Valley bottom	5.4	4.4	198	10	188	0.05
	μ	5.4	4.5	51.5	6	45.6	0.3
	SD \pm	0.17	0.16	81.96	2.36	79.67	0.13
	CV%	3.15	3.55	159.14	39.33	174.71	43.3

Fe_d=Dithionite extractable Fe, Fe_o=Oxalate extractable Fe, Fe_o/Fe_d= Fe-ratio

A= Sedimentary Toposequence, B= Basement Complex Toposequence

μ = mean

SD \pm = standard deviation

Cv%= coefficient of variation

Table 5 Correlation Models of Some Soil Properties

Soil Properties	Correlation Model	r	
		A	B
Clay	Fe _d /Clay Vs Clay	-0.913**	NS
Silt	Fe _d /Clay Vs Silt	0.588*	0.887**
Fe _d	Fe _d Vs Fe _d -Fe _o	0.806**	1.00**

r = Correlation Coefficient, * = 0.05 significant level, ** = 0.01 significant level

NS = non-significant, Fe_d = Dithionite Extractable, A = Sedimentary Toposequence

B = Basement Complex Toposequence

Received for Publication: 08/10/2011

Accepted for Publication: 20/11/2011

Corresponding author

Enya, O.O,

Agronomy Department, University of Ibadan, Ibadan. Nigeria.

Email: osimenya@yahoo.com